
Impact of Metadata Quality for Effective Information Retrieval in Institutional Repositories of Federal Universities in North-Central, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Background: Institutional Repositories (IRs) are essential tools for knowledge sharing, enhancing access, visibility, and usability of scholarly resources. However, their information retrieval is often hindered by poor metadata quality. Hence, this study aims to investigate the impact of metadata quality on information retrieval in institutional repositories among librarians and postgraduate students in federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria.

Methodology: A descriptive survey design was adopted, combining quantitative and qualitative approaches. The population comprised 24 ICT librarians and 12,944 postgraduate students from six federal universities with functional repositories. A total enumeration was used for ICT librarians, while a sample of 373 postgraduate students was selected using Krejcie and Morgan's table and proportionate sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and an observation checklist, validated by experts and tested for reliability with a Cronbach's Alpha coefficient of 0.75. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics and Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient at a 0.05 level of significance, using SPSS software.

Findings/Results: Findings revealed that journal articles, theses, books, software, and book chapters were the most common resources in the repositories. In contrast, multimedia resources, such as videos, animations, and technical reports, were less frequently available. A strong positive correlation ($R = 0.651$; $p < 0.05$) was found between metadata quality and information retrieval, indicating that improved metadata enhances accessibility. Challenges identified included limited search functionalities, copyright restrictions, low ICT skills, inadequate funding, and inconsistent metadata.

Implications: The study highlights that enhancing metadata quality directly improves access to digital resources, thereby boosting research productivity and visibility.

Conclusion: The study concluded that metadata quality plays a crucial role in enabling accurate and efficient information retrieval, thereby maximising the potential of institutional repositories.

Recommendations: The study recommended improved funding, provision of diverse digital resources, and training for ICT librarians and postgraduate students to strengthen metadata practices and ensure effective information retrieval.

Keywords: Metadata, Information retrieval, Institutional repository, Federal universities, North-Central, Nigeria

INTRODUCTION

In today's knowledge-driven world, effective information retrieval serves as the gateway to invaluable data and resources. For federal universities in North-Central Nigeria, quick and precise access to institutional knowledge is essential for fostering academic growth and

innovation. However, the effectiveness of retrieving information from these institutional repositories is closely correlated with the quality of metadata. High-quality metadata enhances precision, recall, and relevance in search results, while poor metadata often leads to missed resources, user frustration, and reduced utility of repositories (Zeng & Qin, 2020). Thus, metadata quality and effective information retrieval are interdependent, with the former serving as the foundation for the latter.

Historically, the development of information retrieval systems has been closely tied to the evolution of metadata. Early library catalogues relied on descriptive bibliographic records to support discovery, a tradition traceable to Cutter's *Rules for a Dictionary Catalogue* (1904), which stressed the importance of accurate descriptive elements for effective retrieval. With the advent of digital libraries in the late 20th century, metadata standards such as Dublin Core (Zavalina & Burke, 2021) emerged to provide structured descriptions of digital resources. Studies (such as Ulrich & Kock-Schoppenhauer, 2022; Masa'Deh *et al.*, 2021; Nogueras-Iso *et al.*, 2021; and Elouataoui, 2024) have consistently demonstrated that the completeness, accuracy, and consistency of metadata directly impact the efficiency of information retrieval. In institutional repositories, metadata functions as the backbone that connects users to stored knowledge through attributes such as author, title, subject, publication date, abstracts, and keywords. Therefore, understanding the historical evolution of metadata and its correlation with information retrieval is crucial for examining how metadata quality influences the effectiveness of institutional repositories in Nigerian federal universities.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Ideally, institutional repositories should provide seamless access to academic resources through accurate and consistent metadata, thereby enhancing discovery, retrieval, and research visibility (Nneka & Kaosisochukwu, 2021). However, in federal universities in North-Central Nigeria, this ideal is undermined by inconsistent and inaccurate metadata, coupled with challenges such as poor ICT skills, low bandwidth, inadequate funding, and unstable power supply (Saliu *et al.*, 2022). These shortcomings affect researchers, lecturers, librarians, and students who struggle to retrieve relevant information efficiently, leading to frustration, reduced productivity, and limited visibility of scholarly publications. Addressing these issues requires improving metadata standards, enhancing staff capacity, and strengthening institutional support. Although institutional repositories have been widely studied globally (Kato *et al.*, 2021), little attention has been given to metadata quality in Nigerian federal universities, particularly in the North-Central zone. This research, therefore, seeks to fill this gap by examining how metadata quality influences effective information retrieval in this context.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What type of information resources are available in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria?
2. What is the influence of metadata quality on the effectiveness of information retrieval in the institutional repositories of the federal university in North-Central, Nigeria?
3. What challenges hinder the effective access and use of information resources in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

The following null hypothesis were developed and tested using a 0.05 significance level:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between metadata quality and information retrieval in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information Retrieval

The effectiveness of any library is determined by how quickly its users can find accurate and relevant information for their diverse needs. According to Rashid (2020), “information retrieval is the process of obtaining the right information for the right user at the right time, focusing on how information is represented, stored, organised, and accessed. It also involves obtaining relevant information resources from a collection of resources. Temitope (2022) suggested that “information retrieval encompasses all activities related to organising, processing, and accessing information in various forms and formats. It enables people to interact with an information system or service to locate information, including text, images, audio, or video that meets their specific needs”.

Echem and Udo-Anyanwu (2018) emphasised that a library's effectiveness as an educational tool hinges on its capability to equip clientele with the necessary resources to retrieve and access information. Retrieval tools empower information seekers to quickly and easily find the information they're looking for. Umelo and Nyemezu (2023) defined “information access or retrieval tools as systems that simplify the process of locating information within an organised institutional repository. They view these tools as fundamental components for systems that organise recorded information collected by libraries, archives, and museums. According to Eserada and Okolo (2019), “information access or retrieval tools, sometimes referred to as finding aids, are created specifically to direct clients to some particular types of information materials. Catalogues, indexes, abstracts, and bibliographies are examples of traditional instruments of the library. In recent times, advances in information and communication technologies (ICTs) have led to the development of computerised access tools that provide not only bibliographic records but also full-text access to digital documents.

Afebende and Nna-Etuk (2019) conducted a study to examine how information retrieval tools impact the usage of libraries among federal university undergraduate students located in the South-South zone of Nigeria. The study included 952 registered library users were used as the population of the study selected from three universities in the region during the 2017-2018 academic session. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, where a structured questionnaire was the only data collection instrument. The collected data was analysed using standard deviation and mean. Simple linear and multiple regression analyses were both used to test the hypothesis. A regression coefficient value of $R=.489$ was yielded, indicating a strong positive correlation between utilisation of library resources and knowledge of information retrieval tools. The study also highlighted that there was a relatively low level of awareness regarding information retrieval tools among the institutions examined. As a recommendation, the authors suggested that greater emphasis should be placed on teaching library user education programmes on the use of information retrieval tools. While Afebende and Nna-Etuk (2019) examined the impact of library resources on information retrieval tools among undergraduate students in traditional libraries in the South-South region of Nigeria, the current study specifically addressed metadata quality and content organisation for effective information retrieval in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria.

Afebende and Nna-Etuk's (2019) study is relevant to this current study as they both enhance library services and user experiences in university settings by identifying factors that impact the effectiveness of information retrieval.

Metadata Quality

Zeng and Qin (2020) referred to metadata as a specific type of information, detailing data or information concerning other resources like books, audio files, scientific datasets, or digital images. Although technically plural, it is commonly used in a singular form, much like the term "data." It enables individuals to perform functions related to the information resources it pertains to, even when embedded within a digital resource. The term itself originates from the combination of the Greek prefix "meta," signifying "after" or "higher," and the Latin word "data," referring to processed information, including books and films.

1. **Meta:** after, abstract or conceptual; relating to a higher level of abstraction.
2. **Data:** bits of information processed by computers and by extension any information-bearing entity, including books and films.
3. **Metadata:** data about data or information about information resources.

Metadata Standards

As reported by Horodyski (2022), a standard is a collectively agreed-upon level of excellence that serves as a benchmark or guideline in comparative assessments. This requires regular assessment, a responsibility falling on the metadata manager or taxonomist. If your industry necessitates such benchmarks, it is advisable to adhere to and possibly adapt to an industry standard, if applicable. Industry professionals create these standards to address the specific requirements of their field. Embracing standards can lead to significant cost savings. Some widely used standards today include MARC, ONIX, Dublin Core, MODS, METS, XMP, PRISM, SMPTE, and IPTC.

Structure of a Dublin Core Metadata

Table 1: Metadata Standards

Metadata Subtag	Description
Author (s)	The person(s) who are the owners of the resources
Title	The name given to the resources.
Description	Detailed information on the resource content
Date	The date the resources were published
Publisher	A person or organisation in charge of publishing the document
Citation	Citing the resource
Series name	The name of the series and the number assigned to the resources
Subject	The topic of the content of the document
Type	The nature of the resource, whether it is a book, a thesis or an article
Identifier	A number that identifies the resource uniquely, such as a DOI (digital object identifier)
Abstract	A summary of the content of the document
Source	Referencing the source, the present document is derived from
ISSN/ISBN	A standard number confirming the authenticity of the resource
Language	The resource language
Rights	Rights of the resource.

The choice of a metadata standard depends on your specific goals. It is crucial to deeply understand the metadata standards relevant to your industry or application. Active engagement with the standards community, by sharing insights and updates with the governing body, can

further enhance your understanding and contribute to the evolution of these standards (Horodyski, 2022).

Mosha and Ngulube (2023) conducted a systematic review of 13 studies selected from 1,597 papers published between 2003 and 2023, focusing on metadata standards for preserving, discovering, and reusing research data in repositories. The review highlighted the use of descriptive, structural, and administrative metadata, but found limited evidence on their practical application in enhancing discovery and reuse. It also noted the absence of specific higher education institutions actively employing such standards. Key challenges identified included poor repository design, lack of expertise, and limited technological capacity. The study underscores the importance of metadata in shaping institutional repository practices and guiding stakeholder decision-making. The current study provided empirical evidence from Nigerian universities, showing how metadata quality and content organisation directly impact postgraduate students' ability to retrieve information. In contrast, Mosha & Ngulube (2023) conducted a global literature review to understand how metadata standards can support the preservation, discovery, and reuse of research data in repositories. Both studies highlight the central role of metadata in academic repositories.

Institutional Repositories (IR) in Nigeria

Across Africa, universities and other educational institutions are increasingly adopting technology to improve efficiency and drive development. A key part of this effort involves digitising and preserving academic content, a task primarily handled by university libraries, which act as caretakers of the institution's intellectual output (Kodua-Ntim and Fombad, 2020). This focus on organising and making scholarly materials available in a digital format is often called digitisation.

According to Nneka and Kaosisochukwu (2021), an institutional repository (IR) is a digital platform managed by an academic institution to collect, store, and share the scholarly work produced by its faculty, researchers, and students. This content can include various materials such as research articles, theses, dissertations, conference papers, and more. The main goal of an IR is to enhance the accessibility, visibility, and impact of an institution's intellectual work by providing a central location for storing and organising these materials (Abduldayan et al., 2021). Furthermore, these repositories play a crucial role in safeguarding digital content for the long term, ensuring it remains accessible for future generations (Nwokedi & Nwokedi, 2018).

Saliu *et al.* (2022) conducted a study on challenges and strategies related to the utilisation of Institutional Repositories (IRs) among South West, Nigeria, library academic staff. The research aimed to identify the primary obstacles to using IRs and propose effective strategies to address them. The study was guided by two objectives. The study utilised a descriptive survey; data were gathered from 420 academic staff across six federal universities through a questionnaire designed specifically for the study objectives. Findings highlighted several challenges, including poor ICT skills, reluctance to deposit research materials, power supply issues, absence of IR policies, copyright concerns, financial constraints, and limited awareness of publisher policies. Proposed strategies to overcome these challenges included providing alternative power sources, improving Internet bandwidth, implementing IR policies, offering plagiarism detection software, clarifying copyright and intellectual property rights, and enhancing awareness about the significance and content of IRs. The study by Saliu *et al.* (2022) focuses on challenges and strategies related to the utilisation of Institutional Repositories (IRs) among academic staff in libraries in the South West, Nigeria. On the other hand, the current study investigates metadata quality and content organisation for effective information retrieval

in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria. Both studies are relevant to the improvement of library services and academic research within Nigerian university settings.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design with a mixed-method approach to gather data from ICT librarians and postgraduate students across federal universities in North-Central Nigeria with functional institutional repositories. The population comprised 24 ICT librarians and 12,944 postgraduate students. A total enumeration approach was used for ICT librarians, while a sample size of 373 postgraduate students was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's table. Proportionate sampling ensured fair representation from each university. Data collection instruments included a structured questionnaire and an observation checklist. The questionnaire, divided into demographic and research question sections, employed a 4-point Likert scale to capture perceptions of metadata quality and information retrieval. The observation checklist was used to identify types of information resources in the repositories. Validity was ensured through expert review by supervisors and lecturers, while reliability was tested through a pilot study at the University of Nigeria, Nsukka, using Cronbach's Alpha, which produced a coefficient of 0.75, confirming reliability. Data analysis involved descriptive statistics (frequency counts, percentages, mean, and standard deviation) for research questions and Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient at a 0.05 significance level to test the hypothesis, using SPSS software for analysis.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Response Rate

A total of 373 questionnaires were distributed to postgraduate students, and 269 were returned as usable, resulting in a 72% response rate. Additionally, 24 questionnaires were administered to ICT librarians at the same institutions. Out of these, 15 copies were completed, returned, and found usable, representing a 63% response rate. The checklist, which was answered by ICT librarians, was used to assess the availability of the types of information resources within their repositories.

Table 4.1: Response Rate of Questionnaire by Category of the Respondents

S/N	Name of Federal University	AQ-Lib	QR-Lib	RR(%)	AQ-ICT	QR-ICT	RR(%)
1	Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State	58	46	79%	6	4	67%
2	University of Abuja, FCT	71	44	62%	4	2	50%
3	Federal University, Lafia, Nasarawa State	59	46	78%	3	2	67%
4	Federal University Lokoja, Kogi State	56	44	79%	2	2	100%
5	University of Ilorin, Kwara State	68	44	65%	4	3	75%
6	University of Jos, Plateau State	61	45	74%	5	2	40%
	Total	373	269	72%	24	15	63%

Key: Administered Questionnaires to Librarians (AQ-Lib), Questionnaires Returned from Librarians (QR-Lib), Return Rate (RR-Lib), Administered Questionnaires to ICT (AQ-ICT), Questionnaires Returned from (QR-ICT), Return Rate (%)

4.2 Research Question One

What are the types of information resources available in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central Nigeria?

Table 4.2: Information Resources Available

Information Resources	Federal University of Technology, Minna		University of Abuja		Federal University, Lafia		Federal University Lokoja		University of Ilorin		University of Jos	
	AV	NA	AV	NA	AV	NA	AV	NA	AV	NA	AV	NA
Journal Articles	√		√		√		√		√		√	
Books	√		√		√		√		√		√	
Theses	√		√		√		√		√		√	
Audio files		X	√			X		X	√		√	
Videos		X		X		X		X	√		√	
Animations		X		X		X		X				X
Images	√			X		X		X	√		√	
Technical Report	√		√			X		X	√		√	
Software	√		√		√		√		√		√	
Book chapter	√		√		√		√		√		√	

Key: Available (√), Not Available (x)

Table 4.2 showed the information resources available and those not available in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-central, Nigeria. Six (6) of the federal universities had journal articles, books, theses, software and book chapters which were available in all the Federal University libraries (Minna, Abuja, Lafia, Lokoja, Ilorin and Jos) respectively. Similarly, four (4) Federal University libraries (Minna, Abuja, Ilorin and Jos) had technical reports. On the other hand, videos were not available in four (4) of the Federal University libraries (Minna, Abuja, Lokoja and Lafia). Similarly, animations were unavailable in all six (6) federal university libraries. The finding revealed the availability of journal articles, books, theses, book chapters, technical reports and software, while animations, videos and audio files were absent.

Research Question 2: What is the influence of metadata quality on the effectiveness of information retrieval in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central Nigeria?

Table 4.3: Metadata Quality for Effective Information Retrieval (Postgraduate students)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	n	FX	\bar{x}	STD	Decision
		4	3	2	1	269				
1	Contents in the repository are accurate and up-to-date	101	95	50	23	269	812	3.02	0.52	Agreed
2	The authors are professionals in their various fields	91	105	55	18	269	807	3.00	0.50	Agreed
3	Information on the repository can be easily understood and used	108	104	44	13	269	850	3.16	0.66	Agreed
4	Contents from the repository are well-described for easy access	107	122	32	8	269	866	3.22	0.72	Agreed
5	There is consistency in the way the contents are organised	110	102	47	10	269	850	3.16	0.66	Agreed
6	The institutional repository adheres to the rules and guidelines used by other repositories	94	103	49	23	269	806	2.99	0.49	Agreed
7	The contents in the repository are complete	87	93	58	31	269	774	2.88	0.38	Disagreed
8	The repository provides an option to choose different languages	90	99	59	21	269	796	2.95	0.45	Disagreed
9	Each content is unique to an author	92	99	45	33	269	788	2.93	0.43	Disagreed
Average Weighted mean								2.98		

Key: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), Strongly Disagreed (SD), n = Number of Retrieved Copies of Questionnaire, \bar{X} =Mean and (Average Weighted mean = 2.98)

Table 4.3 showed the responses of postgraduate students on the role of metadata quality for effective information retrieval in institutional repositories. Out of the nine items listed, five items produced high mean scores, which were above the average weighted mean of 2.98. These items include item 4: Contents from the repository are well described for easy access (\bar{x} =3.22; SD=0.72),

item 5: There is consistency with the way contents are organised (\bar{x} =3.16; SD=0.66), item 1: Contents in the repository are accurate and up-to-date (\bar{x} =3.02; SD=0.52), item 2: The authors are professionals in their various fields (\bar{x} =3.00; SD=0.50) and item 6: The institutional repository adheres to rules and guidelines used by other repositories (\bar{x} =2.99; SD=0.49). On the other hand, four items produced low mean scores, which were below the average weighted mean of 2.98. These items include item 8: The repository provides an option to choose different languages (\bar{x} =2.95; SD=0.45), item 9: Each content is unique to an author (\bar{x} =2.93; SD=0.43), item 7: Contents on the repository are complete (\bar{x} =2.88; SD=0.38) and item 3: Information on the repository can be easily understood and used by different kinds of computers and software (\bar{x} =2.72; SD=0.22). The average weighted mean of 2.98 and above is considered the mean rate of metadata quality for effective information retrieval in institutional repositories, while the average weighted mean below 2.98 is not considered to have good quality for information retrieval in institutional repositories. From the findings, the study revealed that items 1, 2, 4, 5 and 6 were rated strongly agree, while items 3, 7, 8 and 9 were disagreed by the respondents as metadata quality for information retrieval in an institutional repository. It can be deduced that metadata contents are accurate, complete, up-to-date, consistent and easily understood.

Table 4.4: Challenges Faced in accessing and using Information resources in the Institutional Repositories (Postgraduate students)

S/N	Statements	SA	A	D	SD	n	FX	\bar{x}	STD	Decision
		4	3	2	1	269				
1	Inconsistent and incomplete Metadata	79	88	52	50	269	734	2.73	0.23	Disagreed
2	Poor content organisation	97	118	39	15	269	835	3.10	0.60	Agreed
3	Limited search functionality	91	95	60	23	269	792	2.94	0.44	Disagreed
4	Interoperability challenges	80	99	59	31	269	766	2.85	0.35	Disagreed
5	Varying user needs and preferences	85	123	47	14	269	817	3.04	0.54	Agreed
6	Copyright and access challenges	101	90	55	23	269	807	3.00	0.50	Agreed
7	Ineffective users' search skills	99	108	38	24	269	820	3.05	0.55	Agreed
8	User interface and experience challenges	69	99	59	42	269	733	2.72	0.22	Disagreed
9	Lack of funds to create and maintain an IR	112	130	19	8	269	884	3.29	0.79	Agreed
Average weighted mean								2.96		

Key: Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), Strongly Disagreed (SD), n = Number of Retrieved Copies of Questionnaire, \bar{X} =Mean and (Average weighted mean = 2.96)

Table 4.4 shows the responses of postgraduate students on the challenges faced in retrieving information from the institutional repositories. Out of nine items listed, high mean scores above the average weighted mean of 2.96 were five items. There are item 9: Lack of funds to create and maintain an IR (\bar{x} =3.29; SD=0.79), item 2: Poor content organisation (\bar{x} =3.10; SD=0.60), item 1: I am satisfied with the information retrieval system (\bar{x} =3.02; SD=0.51), item 7: Ineffective users' search skills (\bar{x} =3.05; SD=0.55), item 5: Varying user needs and preferences (\bar{x} =3.04; SD=0.54)

and item 6: Copyright and access challenges ($\bar{x}=3.00$; $SD=0.50$). In contrast, low mean scores were recorded by four items below the average weighted mean of 2.96. This shows these items were not the main challenges faced by postgraduate students towards retrieving information from the institutional repositories.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESES

H₀₁ There is no significant relationship between metadata quality and information retrieval in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria.

Table 4.5: Relationship between Metadata Quality and Information Retrieval in the Institutional Repositories

Variables	Std.		N	DF	R	P-value
	Mean	Deviation				
Metadata quality	32.26	3.20	269	267	.651**	0.00
Information Retrieval	62.62	10.63	269			

* $P < 0.05$ is significant, *DF*: degree of Freedom; ***R* = correlation

Table 4.5 showed a significant relationship between metadata quality and information retrieval in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria. This is because the calculated p-value of 0.000 is lower than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, and the value of correlation $R = 0.651$, which is positive. This implies that the relationship between metadata quality and information retrieval in the institutional repositories among postgraduate students is positive and strong. This implies that increasing the quality of metadata would enhance information retrieval by postgraduate students. Therefore, the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant relationship between metadata quality and information retrieval in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-Central, Nigeria is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of the study as regards research question 1 revealed that information resources such as journal articles, books, theses, software and book chapters were available in the institutional repositories of federal universities in North-central, Nigeria. The availability of these information resources in the institutional repositories of the federal universities could be because of the publish or perish syndrome, where university lecturers are required or obligated to publish articles in journals or present papers in both national and international conferences and publish books in a chapter for their promotion. This could be why these information resources are available in the institutional repositories. Another reason could be to increase the visibility of lecturers and faculty members based on their research outputs on the repositories. This aligns with the observation of Abduldayan *et al.* (2021) who reported that institutional repositories serve as centralised repositories for storing and organising scholarly materials such as research data, articles, conference papers and all intellectual output from the institution, making them easily discoverable and accessible to a global audience.

On the other hand, videos, animations, audio files, images and technical reports were not available in some institutional repositories of federal universities. The reason could be because of the inability of students to search and browse information resources from the institutional repositories for their information and research needs. This supports the findings of Begum and Elahi (2022), who stressed that without the capability to search and browse, this collection of digital objects is of little use. However, Begum and Elahi (2022) stated further that IRs contain a variety of digital content, including structured and unstructured text, statistical data, images, and multimedia, to mention but a few, stored on different storage media like hard disks, CD-ROMs, DVD-ROMs, and floppies.

The study findings regarding research question 2 showed that postgraduate students moderately agreed that metadata quality affects the retrieval of information from institutional repositories. Based on the influence of metadata quality for effective information retrieval in repositories, postgraduate students indicated that all the contents in the repositories are accurate and up-to-date, authors whose works are deposited in the institutional repositories are professionals in their various fields, contents from the repositories are well described for easy access, there is consistency with the way contents are organised and the institutional repositories adheres to rules and guidelines used by other repositories. This could be because postgraduate students can access information resources from the repositories easily and at the right time. This is in line with the observation of Raghavendra-Nayaka and Ranjan (2023), who pointed out that accurate and comprehensive metadata improves the precision and recall rates of search results. This corroborates the observation of Rashid (2020), who defined information retrieval as the process of obtaining accurate information at the right time for the right user, focusing on how information is represented, stored, organised, and accessed.

On the other hand, the majority of the postgraduate students disagreed based on the role of metadata quality for effective information retrieval in repositories, that information on the repositories can be easily understood and used, the contents on the repository are complete, provides an option to choose different languages, and each content is unique to an author. This is in contrast with the findings of Mayernik (2021), who reported that the various definitions, functions and roles demonstrate that metadata is not a fixed and singular concept; instead, it is a flexible, varied and fractional idea.

In research question 5, the opinion of the respondents differed as to what they feel are challenges faced in retrieving information from the institutional repositories. Postgraduate students indicated that limited search functionality, varying user needs and preferences, copyright and access challenges, ineffective users' search skills and lack of funds to create and maintain an IR constitute their challenges, while limited search functionality, varying user needs and preferences, copyright and access challenges, user interface and experience challenges and lack of funds to create and maintain an IR constitute what the ICT librarians see as challenges to information retrieval from the institutional repositories.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study underscored that the effective provision of information resources underpinned by high-quality metadata is critical to fulfilling the core mandate of academic

libraries, regardless of type. In the context of federal universities in North-Central Nigeria, the study established that metadata standards significantly influenced postgraduate students' ability to retrieve needed information. The challenges of retrieving information include inadequate search functionalities, poor user search skills, limited funding, and copyright restrictions. Addressing these challenges is not optional but essential: unless institutional repositories are properly developed, maintained, and supported, the potential of digital resources would remain underutilised. Stakeholders, especially university administrators, ICT librarians, and policymakers, must prioritise strategic investment in repository infrastructure, user training, and metadata quality to unlock the full benefits of institutional repositories for postgraduate research and academic development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The management of federal universities should ensure adequate information materials are provided, especially videos, animations, images and technical reports, which appear to be missing in the institutional repositories of some of the universities.
2. The management of federal universities should provide or organise training sessions for ICT librarians and postgraduate students through workshops and symposia on the various definitions and functions of metadata quality for effective information retrieval in institutional repositories. This would provide consistency in the way content is organised and provide options to choose from different languages in the repository.
3. The management of federal universities should ensure that adequate funds are provided to create and maintain their repositories.

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